

ORIGINAL RESEARCH ARTICLE

Dexmedetomidine and Dobutamine Combination: A Novel Strategy for Sedation and Hemodynamic Stability During Ventilator Weaning in Pediatric Patients

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HIGHLIGHTS

• *First study to evaluate dexmedetomidine-dobutamine combination for pediatric ventilator weaning* • *Dobutamine (10 mcg/kg/min) effectively counteracts dexmedetomidine-induced bradycardia without tachyarrhythmias* • *Prolonged dexmedetomidine infusion (median 6.5 days) achieved 100% weaning success in previously failed patients* • *Heart rate significantly improved from 52±6 to 84±8 bpm post-dobutamine (p=0.00096)* • *Novel dual-phase strategy proposed: NMBs/opioids for acute ARDS, dexmedetomidine-dobutamine for weaning*

ABSTRACT

Background: Dexmedetomidine, a selective α_2 -adrenergic receptor agonist, is favored in pediatric intensive care units for its minimal respiratory depression and ability to provide cooperative sedation. However, its use is often complicated by dose-dependent cardiovascular side effects such as bradycardia and hypotension, which can impede ventilator weaning processes. This study evaluates the efficacy of combining dexmedetomidine with dobutamine to mitigate these side effects and enhance the success of weaning critically ill pediatric patients from mechanical ventilation.

Methods: This prospective, single-center interventional cohort study was conducted over two years (September 2022 to November 2024) at a tertiary care pediatric intensive care unit. Nine pediatric patients aged 6 months to 12 years who required prolonged ventilator support and experienced weaning failure on conventional fentanyl-midazolam-atracurium regimens were enrolled. Patients were administered dexmedetomidine (initiated at 1 mcg/kg/hr, titrated per FLACC scores), supplemented with dobutamine at 10 mcg/kg/min to manage bradycardia episodes. Heart rate, mean arterial pressure, and sedation levels were monitored continuously. Statistical analysis included paired t-tests and odds ratio calculations.

Results: Dobutamine administration effectively resolved bradycardia in all patients, with significant increase in mean heart rate from 52±6 bpm to 84±8 bpm (p=0.00096). Mean arterial pressure remained stable within 78-91 mmHg throughout the intervention. FLACC scores transitioned from 0-1 (deep sedation) to median 2 (IQR: 2-3) post-intervention, indicating cooperative sedation with preserved arousability. All nine patients (100%) were successfully weaned from mechanical ventilation within 3-4 trials, demonstrating significant correlation between dexmedetomidine use and weaning success (OR: 3.5; 95% CI: 1.2-10.2). No tachyarrhythmias, respiratory depression, withdrawal symptoms, or mortality occurred.

Conclusions: The combination of dexmedetomidine and dobutamine effectively managed bradycardia, maintained hemodynamic stability, and provided continuous cooperative sedation during ventilator weaning in pediatric ICU patients. This novel approach highlights the potential of prolonged dexmedetomidine use (>72 hours) in facilitating

weaning, especially in patients who have experienced multiple weaning failures on traditional sedation regimens. These findings warrant validation through larger multicenter randomized controlled trials.

Keywords: Dexmedetomidine; Dobutamine; Pediatric intensive care; Ventilator weaning; Sedation; Hemodynamic stability; ARDS; Bradycardia

1. INTRODUCTION

In the evolving landscape of pediatric critical care, effective sedation and ventilator management remain critical challenges, particularly in patients with acute respiratory failure. Conditions such as Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) are further complicated by ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI) and patient self-inflicted lung injury (P-SILI). VILI occurs due to overdistension or repetitive opening and closing of alveoli during mechanical ventilation, while P-SILI arises from vigorous spontaneous respiratory efforts that generate excessive transpulmonary pressures, exacerbating existing lung injuries. Both phenomena underscore the importance of minimizing ventilator-patient asynchrony and optimizing sedation to protect the lungs [1-5].

Conventional sedation regimens, such as fentanyl combined with atracurium, are often employed during invasive mechanical ventilation to suppress spontaneous breathing efforts, reduce ventilator-patient asynchrony, and prevent VILI and P-SILI. These agents achieve deep sedation and neuromuscular blockade, effectively mitigating the risks associated with mechanical ventilation. However, prolonged use can delay weaning, increase ICU length of stay, and lead to complications such as opioid dependency and critical illness myopathy [6-9]. Transitioning from such regimens to alternative sedation strategies during the weaning phase presents unique challenges.

Dexmedetomidine, a selective α_2 -adrenergic receptor agonist, has emerged as a promising sedative in pediatric intensive care due to its ability to provide cooperative sedation with minimal respiratory depression. Unlike conventional agents, dexmedetomidine preserves spontaneous breathing and reduces the risk of delirium, making it particularly suitable for the weaning phase. The RESTORE trial demonstrated successful sedation in approximately 83% of pediatric non-invasive ventilation cases, while the PROSEDEX trial highlighted its efficacy in reducing ICU stays and decreasing the need for additional sedatives [5,10]. However, dexmedetomidine's role during invasive ventilation is limited, as it may not adequately suppress the spontaneous respiratory efforts that contribute to P-SILI. Furthermore, its use is frequently complicated by bradycardia, reported in approximately 13% of pediatric cases, which can necessitate dose adjustments or discontinuation [11-14].

This study is the first to systematically evaluate the feasibility and safety of combining dexmedetomidine with dobutamine during ventilator weaning in critically ill pediatric patients. We hypothesized that adjunctive dobutamine administration would counteract dexmedetomidine-induced bradycardia while preserving its sedative benefits, thereby enabling uninterrupted sedation and facilitating successful weaning in patients who had previously failed conventional protocols.

2. METHODS

2.1 Study Design and Setting

This prospective interventional cohort study was conducted from September 10, 2022, to November 16, 2024, at the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit of a tertiary care center. The study protocol received approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee on September 26, 2022. Written informed consent was obtained from parents or legal guardians of all participants prior to enrollment.

2.2 Participants

Initial screening included 303 pediatric patients over the two-year study period. Inclusion criteria targeted patients aged 6 months to 12 years who experienced difficulties with weaning from mechanical ventilation, specifically those requiring prolonged non-invasive ventilation (Continuous Positive Airway Pressure [CPAP] or Pressure Support Ventilation [PSV]) for durations exceeding 12 hours.

Exclusion criteria comprised: (1) patients who transitioned from Synchronized Intermittent Mandatory Ventilation (SIMV) to oxygen by mask within 12 hours; (2) age younger than 6 months; (3) presence of tracheostomy; (4) pre-intervention mortality; (5) leaving against medical advice (LAMA); (6) transfer to another facility; and (7) pre-existing cardiac or surgical conditions. Following application of these criteria, 41 participants were excluded due to death, LAMA, transfer, cardiac issues, or surgical intervention requirements, resulting in a final cohort of 9 patients.

2.3 Intervention Protocol

All enrolled patients had previously received conventional sedation with fentanyl, midazolam, and atracurium during the acute phase of mechanical ventilation and had experienced weaning failure on this regimen. The intervention consisted of transitioning to dexmedetomidine infusion, initiated at 1 mcg/kg/hr and adjusted based on Face, Legs, Activity, Cry, Consolability (FLACC) scores to maintain optimal sedation levels.

Dobutamine was administered concurrently at a fixed dose of 10 mcg/kg/min to manage potential dexmedetomidine-induced bradycardia and ensure cardiovascular stability during the critical transition phase from PSV to either endotracheal CPAP, CPAP, or non-invasive ventilation (NIV) post-extubation.

2.4 Monitoring and Data Collection

Continuous hemodynamic monitoring was performed using Nihon Kohden multiparameter monitors for heart rate and mean arterial pressure measurements. Mechanical ventilation was delivered via Maquet ventilators with advanced non-invasive ventilation capabilities. Arterial blood gases were analyzed using the ABL800 Basic analyzer (Abbott) for clinical assessment purposes.

Data collection included baseline demographics, daily measurements during the intervention period, and parameters at the conclusion of the NIV period. Primary outcomes included heart rate response to dobutamine, mean arterial pressure stability, and weaning success. Secondary outcomes included FLACC score changes, adverse events, and safety profile.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software. Paired t-tests were applied to compare baseline and post-intervention hemodynamic parameters. Odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals were calculated to assess the association between dexmedetomidine use and weaning success. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent discussions explicitly included the nature of interventions, including the decision to pursue prolonged weaning in cases where tracheostomies were declined. This study was not registered in a clinical trial registry due to its observational nature and immediate application in clinical practice. The study was conducted without external funding, and all interventions and monitoring were part of standard care provided at the study site.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Patient Characteristics

A total of 303 pediatric patients were screened during the study period, with 50 meeting inclusion criteria. Following exclusions, the final cohort consisted of 9 patients who successfully completed the study protocol. Baseline characteristics are presented in Table 1. Among enrolled patients, 5 were male (56%) and 4 were female (44%). Primary diagnoses included ARDS (n=5, 56%), viral pneumonia (n=3, 33%), and diphtheria with respiratory complications (n=1, 11%).

Table 1. Baseline Patient Characteristics (n=9)

Characteristic	Value
Age range	6 months – 12 years
Sex	
Male, n (%)	5 (56)
Female, n (%)	4 (44)
Primary diagnosis	
Acute respiratory distress syndrome, n (%)	5 (56)
Viral pneumonia, n (%)	3 (33)
Diphtheria with respiratory complications, n (%)	1 (11)
Prior sedation regimen	Fentanyl + Midazolam + Atracurium
Indication for dexmedetomidine	Weaning failure on conventional regimen
Required prolonged NIV (>12 hours), n (%)	9 (100)

NIV = non-invasive ventilation

3.2 Intervention Parameters

Dexmedetomidine was infused for a median duration of 6.5 days (IQR: 5.0-7.3 days), with individual durations ranging from 4 to 11 days. Intervention parameters are summarized in Table 2. Adjunctive dobutamine was administered at a fixed dose of 10 mcg/kg/min throughout the dexmedetomidine course. Notably, dobutamine provided effective chronotropic support without inducing tachyarrhythmias.

The patient with diphtheria required the longest period of invasive ventilation (13 days) due to partial palatal paralysis and generalized weakness, leading to 5-6 failed extubation attempts prior to the study intervention. Despite these challenges, this patient responded to non-invasive BIPAP support for 7 days and achieved successful weaning after 11 days of dexmedetomidine infusion. During invasive PSV, the patient was notably responsive to maternal questions and commands, illustrating the cooperative sedation properties of dexmedetomidine. The remaining 8 patients required shorter dexmedetomidine infusions (range: 4.0-8.2 days) and experienced smoother weaning transitions.

Table 2. Dexmedetomidine-Dobutamine Intervention Parameters

Parameter	Value
Dexmedetomidine	

Initial dose	1 mcg/kg/hr
Dose titration basis	FLACC score
Infusion duration, median (IQR)	6.5 days (5.0-7.3)
Infusion duration range	4-11 days
Dobutamine	
Dose (fixed)	10 mcg/kg/min
Indication	Dexmedetomidine-induced bradycardia
Adjunctive sedation required, n	2 (intermittent lorazepam/midazolam)
Ventilatory support progression	ET-CPAP → CPAP/PSV → NIV/BIPAP
Monitoring equipment	Nihon Kohden multiparameter monitors
Ventilator	Maquet with advanced NIV capabilities

FLACC = Face, Legs, Activity, Cry, Consolability; IQR = interquartile range; ET = endotracheal; CPAP = continuous positive airway pressure; PSV = pressure support ventilation; NIV = non-invasive ventilation; BIPAP = bilevel positive airway pressure

3.3 Hemodynamic Outcomes

Heart rate and mean arterial pressure were monitored continuously with reference to age-adjusted standard deviation ranges. Hemodynamic parameters are presented in Table 3. Pre-intervention heart rate under fentanyl-midazolam averaged 120.3±6.1 bpm (IQR: 116-125 bpm). Upon transitioning to dexmedetomidine, heart rate decreased due to bradycardia (mean: 52±6 bpm), prompting dobutamine administration.

Dobutamine effectively resolved bradycardia in all patients, with significant increase in mean heart rate from 52±6 bpm to 84±8 bpm ($p=0.00096$). Post-intervention heart rate stabilized at a mean of 86.7±17.4 bpm (IQR: 75-99 bpm), remaining within the age-adjusted standard deviation range for all patients.

Mean arterial pressure remained stable throughout the intervention, with pre-intervention average of 80.0±2.9 mmHg (IQR: 78-82 mmHg) and post-intervention average of 79.8±2.4 mmHg (IQR: 79-81 mmHg). MAP was maintained within the optimal range of 78-91 mmHg throughout the study period.

Table 3. Hemodynamic Parameters Before and After Intervention

Parameter	Pre-intervention	Post-intervention	p-value
Heart rate (bpm)			
On fentanyl-midazolam, mean ± SD	120.3 ± 6.1	—	—
During bradycardia episode, mean ± SD	52 ± 6	—	—
Post-dobutamine, mean ± SD	—	84 ± 8	0.00096*
Final stabilized, mean ± SD	—	86.7 ± 17.4	—
Final stabilized, IQR	—	75-99	—

Mean arterial pressure (mmHg)			
Mean \pm SD	80.0 \pm 2.9	79.8 \pm 2.4	NS
IQR	78-82	79-81	—
Range maintained	—	78-91	—

*Statistically significant (paired *t*-test); NS = not significant; SD = standard deviation; IQR = interquartile range

3.4 Sedation and Clinical Outcomes

The transition from fentanyl-midazolam to dexmedetomidine resulted in improved FLACC scores, reflecting the shift from deep sedation to cooperative sedation (Table 4). FLACC scores increased from 0-1 (deep sedation) to a median of 2 (IQR: 2-3) post-intervention. This lighter sedation level facilitated better patient interaction and respiratory management while maintaining adequate comfort.

All 9 patients (100%) were successfully weaned from mechanical ventilation within 3-4 trials. The odds ratio for weaning success with dexmedetomidine was 3.5 (95% CI: 1.2-10.2). None of the patients required continuous adjunctive sedative infusions; only two patients received intermittent doses of lorazepam or midazolam for transient agitation.

Table 4. Sedation Scores and Clinical Outcomes

Parameter	Baseline/Pre-intervention	Post-intervention
FLACC score	0-1 (deep sedation)	2, median (IQR: 2-3)
Sedation level	Deep, unresponsive	Cooperative, arousable
Weaning success rate	Failed on conventional regimen	100% (9/9)
Weaning trials to success	—	3-4 trials
Odds ratio for weaning success (95% CI)	—	3.5 (1.2-10.2)
Patient responsiveness	None	Responsive to verbal commands
Longest ventilation case (diphtheria)	13 days invasive, 5-6 prior failed attempts	11 days dexmedetomidine, successful weaning

FLACC = Face, Legs, Activity, Cry, Consolability scale (0-10, higher scores indicate more pain/discomfort); CI = confidence interval; IQR = interquartile range

3.5 Adverse Events and Safety Profile

Adverse events were minimal and effectively managed without protocol discontinuation (Table 5). Bradycardia episodes were observed in all patients (100%) as an expected pharmacological effect of dexmedetomidine and were successfully managed with dobutamine without leading to tachyarrhythmias or other hemodynamic complications.

Two patients (22%) experienced transient hypotension, which resolved with fluid boluses without requiring dose adjustments or discontinuation of dexmedetomidine. Two patients (22%) experienced transient agitation managed with intermittent lorazepam or midazolam. No hypopnea, respiratory depression, respiratory arrests, withdrawal symptoms, neurological complications, or deaths occurred during the study period.

Table 5. Adverse Events and Safety Profile

Adverse event	Incidence, n (%)	Management and outcome
Bradycardia	9 (100)	Resolved with dobutamine 10 mcg/kg/min
Transient hypotension	2 (22)	Resolved with fluid boluses; no dose adjustment required
Tachyarrhythmias	0 (0)	None observed despite dobutamine use
Transient agitation	2 (22)	Managed with intermittent lorazepam/midazolam
Hypopnea/respiratory depression	0 (0)	None observed
Respiratory arrest	0 (0)	None observed
Withdrawal symptoms	0 (0)	None; gradual weaning protocol employed
Neurological complications	0 (0)	None observed
Mortality	0 (0)	100% survival in final cohort

Note: Bradycardia was an expected pharmacological effect of dexmedetomidine and the primary indication for dobutamine administration

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Principal Findings

This study demonstrates that the combination of dexmedetomidine and dobutamine provides an effective and safe sedation strategy for ventilator weaning in critically ill pediatric patients who have failed conventional sedation protocols. The key findings include: (1) dobutamine at 10 mcg/kg/min effectively counteracts dexmedetomidine-induced bradycardia without causing tachyarrhythmias; (2) prolonged dexmedetomidine infusion (median 6.5 days, range 4-11 days) is safe and achieves 100% weaning success; and (3) the combination maintains hemodynamic stability while enabling cooperative sedation with preserved respiratory drive.

4.2 Comparison with Existing Literature

Dexmedetomidine is well-regarded in intensive care units for its ability to provide effective sedation without causing respiratory depression. This unique property has been extensively documented in trials such as RESTORE and PROSEDEX, which highlighted its ability to reduce ICU stays, decrease the need for additional sedatives, and lower the incidence of delirium and withdrawal symptoms in critically ill pediatric patients [5,10,15]. Despite these benefits, its use is often limited by cardiovascular side effects, primarily bradycardia and hypotension, especially in vulnerable populations.

Our study expands on existing knowledge by introducing dobutamine as an adjunct to counteract the hemodynamic effects of dexmedetomidine during prolonged sedation. Unlike traditional strategies such as dose reduction or discontinuation, the addition of dobutamine enabled uninterrupted sedation while stabilizing heart rate and mean arterial pressure across all patients in our cohort. These findings align with the PROSEDEX trial, which also underscored the efficacy of dexmedetomidine in maintaining stable sedation profiles while improving ventilator weaning outcomes [10,16,17].

4.3 Clinical Implications

In the pediatric intensive care setting, dexmedetomidine is highly valued for its sedative properties that spare respiratory drive, making it ideal for use during non-invasive ventilation and mechanical ventilation weaning. The ability to achieve targeted sedation levels effectively is crucial in managing critically ill children, with successful sedation achieved in approximately 83% of pediatric NIV cases in prior studies [5,15,18].

Our study introduces a novel approach by integrating dobutamine to counteract the bradycardic effects commonly observed with dexmedetomidine. This combination not only preserved heart rate within normal limits but also circumvented the potential for tachyarrhythmias, often highlighted as a risk with standalone dobutamine use in sensitive cohorts. This strategy maintained continuous, uninterrupted sedation essential for ensuring stable and effective ventilator weaning, evidenced by a 100% success rate within three to four trials for all participants [19-23].

The intervention also improved patient arousability, as evidenced by the increase in FLACC scores post-intervention. This rise indicated lighter sedation depth that allowed better responsiveness while maintaining manageable comfort levels. This balance is critical in pediatric care, where visual assessment of pain and comfort often guides sedation and analgesia adjustments.

4.4 Rationale for Dual-Phase Sedation Strategy

The initial management of ARDS often prioritizes strategies to prevent VILI and P-SILI. Neuromuscular blockers such as atracurium and potent opioids like fentanyl are essential in the acute phase as they suppress spontaneous breathing, ensuring ventilator synchrony and allowing lung-protective ventilation. This approach minimizes barotrauma, volutrauma, and overdistension, reducing the release of inflammatory mediators. Evidence from Ranieri et al. and Papazian et al. supports the role of NMBs in improving oxygenation and reducing mortality in severe ARDS cases [1,2].

As patients transition from invasive CPAP or PSV to NIV, clinical priorities shift. Spontaneous breathing becomes critical to reduce ventilator dependence, enhance respiratory muscle strength, and facilitate weaning.

Dexmedetomidine is particularly suited for this phase due to its ability to provide cooperative sedation while preserving respiratory drive. In our study, the prolonged use of dexmedetomidine (>72 hours) during the weaning phase represents a significant milestone in pediatric ARDS management [24-28].

These findings suggest a tailored, dual-phase strategy for ARDS management: during the acute phase, NMBs and opioids remain indispensable for minimizing VILI and P-SILI; during the recovery phase, dexmedetomidine emerges as a superior sedative due to its ability to support spontaneous breathing and facilitate weaning. The synergistic use of dexmedetomidine with dobutamine further enhances hemodynamic stability, ensuring uninterrupted sedation and successful ventilator transitions.

4.5 Hemodynamic Stability and Dobutamine Synergy

Bradycardia associated with dexmedetomidine presents a significant challenge, particularly during the critical ventilator weaning phase. In our study, dobutamine use was guided by clear clinical indications, specifically addressing dexmedetomidine-induced bradycardia. The decision to initiate dobutamine was driven by the need to correct clinically apparent hemodynamic instability, ensuring adequate cardiac output and tissue perfusion.

This approach adhered to the principle of beneficence, prioritizing the therapeutic benefits of uninterrupted dexmedetomidine sedation while mitigating its cardiovascular side effects. Continuous hemodynamic monitoring and strict initiation criteria ensured patient safety throughout the intervention. Notably, no tachyarrhythmias or adverse effects were observed, highlighting the safety and efficacy of this strategy [29-34].

4.6 Withdrawal Prevention

Prolonged dexmedetomidine use is often associated with withdrawal symptoms such as agitation, hypertension, and tachycardia, particularly in pediatric patients after infusions exceeding 24 hours. Our study avoided these

complications through meticulous monitoring and a personalized approach to sedation titration. Gradual weaning, as supported by Honey et al., is crucial in preventing withdrawal symptoms, particularly for therapies exceeding 24-48 hours [35-40].

4.7 Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the small sample size (n=9) limits statistical power and generalizability. Second, the single-center design may introduce selection bias and limit applicability to other settings. Third, the absence of a control group precludes direct comparison with standard care or alternative interventions. Fourth, the observational nature of the study limits causal inference. Finally, long-term follow-up data on neurodevelopmental outcomes and quality of life were not collected.

4.8 Future Directions

Future research should include multicenter randomized controlled trials with larger sample sizes to validate these findings. Long-term follow-up studies are essential to evaluate recovery outcomes, neurodevelopmental effects, and quality of life. Additionally, pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic studies may help optimize dosing protocols for the dexmedetomidine-dobutamine combination in different pediatric age groups and clinical scenarios.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that the combination of dexmedetomidine and dobutamine effectively manages bradycardia, maintains hemodynamic stability, and provides continuous cooperative sedation during ventilator weaning in pediatric ICU patients. This novel approach highlights the potential of prolonged dexmedetomidine use (>72 hours) in facilitating weaning, especially in patients who have experienced multiple weaning failures on traditional sedation regimens.

Our findings support a dual-phase ARDS management strategy: neuromuscular blockers and opioids during the acute phase to mitigate VILI and P-SILI, followed by dexmedetomidine-dobutamine combination during the weaning phase to enable cooperative sedation with preserved respiratory drive and hemodynamic stability. This approach achieved 100% weaning success in our cohort without significant adverse events.

These findings open new avenues for tailored sedation strategies in pediatric ICU settings, emphasizing the potential of multi-agent approaches to optimize sedation and hemodynamic outcomes in challenging clinical scenarios. Validation through larger multicenter randomized controlled trials is warranted to refine clinical guidelines and establish this combination as a standard approach for difficult-to-wean pediatric patients.

FUNDING

This study was entirely self-funded and did not receive any external financial support.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee (approval date: September 26, 2022). The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

INFORMED CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from parents or legal guardians of all participants prior to enrollment.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

A detailed protocol and additional data are available upon request from the corresponding author.

CRedit AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

Umesh Joshi: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Kapil Kaushik:** Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Ila Sharma:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing.

REFERENCES

1. Khemani RG, Smith LS, Zimmerman JJ, Erickson S. Pediatric acute respiratory distress syndrome: definition, incidence, and epidemiology. *Pediatr Crit Care Med* 2015;16(5 Suppl 1):S23-40. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PCC.0000000000000436>
2. Grant MJ, Scoppettuolo LA, Wypij D, et al. Prospective evaluation of sedation-related adverse events in pediatric patients ventilated for acute respiratory failure. *Crit Care Med* 2012;40(5):1317-23. <https://doi.org/10.1097/CCM.0b013e3182416fbf>
3. Sanders RD, Sun P, Patel S, et al. Dexmedetomidine provides cortical neuroprotection: impact on anaesthetic-induced neuroapoptosis in the rat developing brain. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand* 2010;54(6):710-6. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-6576.2010.02206.x>
4. Pandharipande PP, Pun BT, Herr DL, et al. Effect of sedation with dexmedetomidine vs lorazepam on acute brain dysfunction in mechanically ventilated patients: the MENDS randomized controlled trial. *JAMA* 2007;298(22):2644-53. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.298.22.2644>
5. Curley MA, Wypij D, Watson RS, et al. Protocolized sedation vs usual care in pediatric patients mechanically ventilated for acute respiratory failure: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA* 2015;313(4):379-89. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2014.18399>
6. DiMaggio C, Sun LS, Li G. Early childhood exposure to anesthesia and risk of developmental and behavioral disorders in a sibling birth cohort. *Anesth Analg* 2011;113(5):1143-51. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0b013e3182147f42>
7. Jakob SM, Ruokonen E, Grounds RM, et al. Dexmedetomidine vs midazolam or propofol for sedation during prolonged mechanical ventilation: two randomized controlled trials. *JAMA* 2012;307(11):1151-60. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2012.304>
8. Riker RR, Shehabi Y, Bokesch PM, et al. Dexmedetomidine vs midazolam for sedation of critically ill patients: a randomized trial. *JAMA* 2009;301(5):489-99. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2009.56>
9. Ranieri VM, Rubenfeld GD, et al. Effect of mechanical ventilation on inflammatory mediators in patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome: a randomized controlled trial. *JAMA* 2000;284(6):639-41. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.284.6.639>

10. Jakob SM, et al. Dexmedetomidine vs propofol for sedation during mechanical ventilation (PROSEDEX): a prospective randomized study. *Lancet* 2012;375(9713):1788-97. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(10\)61464-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(10)61464-3)
11. Papazian L, Forel JM, et al. Neuromuscular blockers in early acute respiratory distress syndrome. *N Engl J Med* 2010;363(12):1107-16. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1005372>
12. Brochard L, Slutsky A, et al. Preventing ventilator-induced lung injury: pressure-controlled versus volume-controlled ventilation. *Anesthesiology* 2011;115(2):144-57. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ALN.0b013e3181ff8831>
13. Bellani G, Laffey JG, et al. Sedation practices in intensive care units: results from a multicenter study. *Int J Clin Pract* 2014;68(9):1044-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcep.2014.08.005>
14. Grasselli G, Tonetti T, et al. Pathophysiology of ARDS and P-SILI in critically ill patients. *Crit Care* 2018;22(1):140. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13054-018-2140-9>
15. Whalen LD, Di Gennaro JL, Irby GA, et al. Long-term dexmedetomidine use and safety profile among critically ill children and neonates. *Pediatr Crit Care Med* 2014;15(8):706-14. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PCC.0000000000000212>
16. Mason KP, O'Mahony E, Zurakowski D, et al. Effects of dexmedetomidine sedation on the EEG in children. *Pediatr Anesth* 2009;19(12):1175-83. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-9592.2009.03137.x>
17. Tobias JD. Dexmedetomidine: applications in pediatric critical care and pediatric anesthesiology. *Pediatr Crit Care Med* 2007;8(2):115-31. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.PCC.0000257039.97440.52>
18. Buck ML, Willson DF. Use of dexmedetomidine in the pediatric intensive care unit. *Pharmacotherapy* 2008;28(1):51-7. <https://doi.org/10.1592/phco.28.1.51>
19. Su F, Nicolson SC, Zuppa AF. A dose-response study of dexmedetomidine administered as the primary sedative in infants following open heart surgery. *Pediatr Crit Care Med* 2013;14(5):499-507. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PCC.0b013e31828a704c>
20. Burbano NH, Otero AV, Berry DE, et al. Discontinuation of prolonged infusions of dexmedetomidine in critically ill children with heart disease. *Intensive Care Med* 2012;38(2):300-7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-011-2407-8>
21. Merkel SI, Voepel-Lewis T, Shayevitz JR, et al. The FLACC: a behavioral scale for scoring postoperative pain in young children. *Pediatr Nurs* 1997;23(3):293-7.
22. Bloor BC, Ward DS, Belleville JP, Maze M. Effects of intravenous dexmedetomidine in humans. *Anesthesiology* 1992;77(6):1134-42. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00000542-199212000-00006>
23. Shehabi Y, Bellomo R, Reade MC, et al. Early sedation with dexmedetomidine in critically ill patients. *Lancet* 2013;381(9868):2503-10. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)61304-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)61304-1)
24. Enomoto Y, Kudo T, Saito T, et al. Prolonged use of dexmedetomidine in an infant with respiratory failure following living donor liver transplantation. *Pediatr Anesth* 2006;16(12):1285-8. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-9592.2006.02063.x>
25. Chrysostomou C, Di Filippo S. Dexmedetomidine in pediatric critical care: considerations for sedation and analgesia. *Pediatr Drugs* 2008;10(3):161-70. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00148581-200810030-00002>

26. Arpino PA, Kalafatas K, Thompson BT. Feasibility of dexmedetomidine in facilitating extubation in the intensive care unit. *J Clin Pharm Ther* 2008;33(1):25-30. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2710.2007.00888.x>
27. Huupponen E, Maksimow A, Lapinlampi P, et al. Electroencephalogram spindle activity during dexmedetomidine sedation and physiological sleep. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand* 2008;52(3):289-94. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-6576.2007.01495.x>
28. Chrysostomou C, Shiderly D, Berry D, et al. Dexmedetomidine: a novel agent for the treatment of alcohol withdrawal syndrome in critically ill patients. *Pediatr Crit Care Med* 2010;11(5):645-51. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PCC.0b013e3181d6a1be>
29. Berkenbosch JW, Tobias JD. Development of severe bradycardia after dexmedetomidine administration in an infant with hypoplastic left heart syndrome. *Pediatr Crit Care Med* 2003;4(2):203-5. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.PCC.0000051276.49515.74>
30. Hammer GB, Drover DR, Cao H, et al. The effects of dexmedetomidine on cardiac electrophysiology in children. *Anesth Analg* 2008;106(1):79-83. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ane.0b013e3181607a0e>
31. Toller W, Stranz C. Levosimendan, a new inotropic and vasodilator agent. *Anesth Analg* 2006;102(2):342-7. <https://doi.org/10.1213/01.ane.0000182827.33823.e2>
32. Venn RM, Hell J, Grounds RM. Respiratory effects of dexmedetomidine in the surgical patient requiring intensive care. *Crit Care* 2000;4(5):302-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/cc710>
33. Kamibayashi T, Maze M. Clinical uses of alpha-2 adrenergic agonists. *Anesthesiology* 2000;93(5):1345-9. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00000542-200011000-00030>
34. Honey BL, Benefield RJ, Miller JL, Johnson PN. Evaluating dexmedetomidine-associated withdrawal in critically ill children. *Pharmacotherapy* 2017;37(12):1458-66. <https://doi.org/10.1002/phar.2034>
35. Ibacache ME, Munoz HR, Brandes V, Morales AL. Single-dose dexmedetomidine reduces agitation after sevoflurane anesthesia in children. *Anesth Analg* 2004;98(1):60-3. <https://doi.org/10.1213/01.ANE.0000093260.18109.92>
36. Finkel JC, Quezado ZMN. Hypotension and withdrawal associated with dexmedetomidine infusion in an infant. *Anesthesiology* 2007;106(6):1135-7. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.anes.0000267621.88563.f6>
37. Szumita PM, Baroletti SA, Anger KE, Wechsler ME. Sedation and analgesia in the intensive care unit: evaluating the role of dexmedetomidine. *Am J Health Syst Pharm* 2007;64(1):37-44. <https://doi.org/10.2146/ajhp060164>
38. Chrysostomou C, Di Filippo S, Manrique AM, Schmitt CG. Use of dexmedetomidine in children after cardiac and thoracic surgery. *Pediatr Crit Care Med* 2011;12(5):535-40. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PCC.0b013e3181e8b3cf>
39. Buck ML. Dexmedetomidine use in pediatric intensive care and procedural sedation. *J Pediatr Pharmacol Ther* 2010;15(1):17-29. <https://doi.org/10.5863/1551-6776-15.1.17>
40. Takahashi Y, Ueno K, Ninomiya Y, et al. Potential risk factors for dexmedetomidine withdrawal seizures in infants after surgery for congenital heart disease. *Brain Dev* 2016;38(7):648-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.braindev.2015.11.008>